

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DEKYEM****FIRST NAME: GIFTY****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 15%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016.

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is using source information without acknowledging the author of the source information.¹**
- Plagiarism is gathering information from different sources purposely to construct a research topic.
- Plagiarism is the ability of the researcher to gather relevant information for the study.
- Plagiarism defines the methodology of research.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D. C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

2. What style guide does Euclid University recommend for its Doctorate in Mediation and Conflict Resolution students, and is this recommendation the only acceptable style?
- Euclid University does not recommend any style but graciously allows its doctoral students to choose what style they want.
 - Euclid University recommends the British English writing style to its English-speaking students as the only style.
 - Euclid University recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian). However, other internationally recognized Rules are fine.²**
 - Euclid University has a style that is mandatory for all doctoral students.
3. List the five general aims of a research project.
- (1) The researcher must have a broad topic. (2) The researcher must identify what is trending in the field. (3) The researcher should always have readers in mind. (4) It is important to gather as much data as possible. (5) The researcher must write clearly.
 - (1) Ask a question worth answering, (2) find an answer that you can support with good reasons, (3) find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons, (4) draft an argument that makes a good case for your answer, and (5) revise that draft until readers think you met the first four goals.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 23.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

- (1) Settle on a few questions, (2) select the most appropriate question, (3) ask your Supervisor whether your choice will meet academic standards, (4) draft the outline of your paper, and (5) get approval from your Supervisor before you commence the project.
 - (1) You must accept the question your Supervisor proposes to the doctoral class, (2) find an answer to the question from your colleagues, (3) proceed to the library to find the necessary data for your work, (4) make sure your argument is related to your question, and (5) revise your draft to check whether your readers will agree with you.
4. What are the three main aims of an introduction and a conclusion in writing a dissertation?
- Introduction: (1) Put your research in the context of other research, (2) make readers understand how your paper addresses the problem they care about, and (3) give them a framework for understanding it (which sometimes, but not always, includes announcing your claim). Conclusion: (a) Leave readers with a clear idea of your claim, (b) make readers understand its importance, and (c) Suggest further research.⁴**
 - Introduction: (1) Evaluate other research, (2) let your readers know you will answer an important question, and (3) walk them through the research. Conclusion: (a) Define your claim, (b) tell your readers your claim is essential, and (c) Evaluate salient concepts in the research.

⁴ Turabian, 110.

- Introduction: (1) First state the purpose of your research, (2) find out if your readers care about the problem you wish to discuss, and (3) suggest a framework for your readers. Conclusion: (a) Repeat your claim verbatim, (b) state why your claim is important, and (c) promise your readers to do further research.
- Introduction: (1) Find similar research for comparison, (2) tell your readers in no uncertain terms that your research is important, and (3) give a framework for your research. Conclusion: (a) Always repeat your claim, (b) indicate the importance of the study, and (c) let your readers know that further research is unnecessary as you have thoroughly researched.
5. What are the proper citations for (1) in-text, (2) footnote, and (3) references for page 6 of the “Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations,” authored by Kate Turabian in 2018, and the Ninth Edition published by the University of Chicago Press in 1996?
- (1) In-text: Madam Kate Turabian, 1996, page 6; (2) Footnote: K., Turabian, “Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” (by University of Chicago Press, 1996), 6; and (3) References: Kate, Turabian. The Manual for Dissertations at Euclid University. Chicago Press. Page 6.
- (1) In-text: (Kate Turabian 2018, 6); (2) Footnote: Turabian, Kate. Manual for writers of term papers, theses, and dissertations, University of Chicago press 2018; and (3) References: Kate Turabian, “Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” (University of Chicago Press, 1996), 6.
- (1) In-text: (Turabian 2018, 6); (2) Footnote: Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (University of Chicago Press,**

1996), 6; and (3) References: Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.⁵

- (1) In-text: (Turabian, Kate. 6); (2) Footnote: Kate Turabian, 2018, “Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” (University of Chicago Press, 1996), 6; and (3) References: Kate Turabian, “Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” (University of Chicago Press, 1996 and 2018), 6.

6. Which of the following sentences is correct regarding special terms in academic writing?

- Italicize and capitalize the definition of non-English terms in a text.
- Italicize terms from another language that are familiar enough to appear in a standard dictionary.
- Italicize proper names from other languages or personal titles that accompany them.
- Italicize isolated words and phrases in languages likely to be unfamiliar to readers of English and capitalize them as in the original language.**⁶

7. What are the initial components of a dissertation, otherwise known as front matter?

- The Introduction Chapter, the Method Chapter, and the Conclusion Chapter.

⁵ Turabian, 141–43.

⁶ Turabian, 322.

- The initial components of the dissertation include Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, and Abstract.⁷**
- The initial components of a dissertation consist of all the data gathered for the dissertation.
- The initial components of a dissertation are the researcher's discussions with the Supervisor before writing the first draft.
8. What is the essence of the successful completion of a dissertation?
- The successful dissertation completion allows the researcher to contribute to the literature while completing the research requirements for the doctoral degree.⁸**
9. Which of the following statements is true?
- Once the researcher has clearly outlined the information needed and the methods to obtain the data, the researcher is ready to develop and present the research design.⁹**
- Extensive engagement with participants is the only method recommended for data collection.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 24.

⁸ Sampson, 10.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 448.

- Focusing on single-source data in qualitative studies is crucial to ensure everything is clear.
- Interviewing is the only source of qualitative data.

10. When constructing a sentence under the European Commission Style Guide, which of the following is true?

- Collective nouns take the plural when the emphasis is on the whole entity but singular when the emphasis is on the individual members.
- When two or more adjectives occur before a noun, an adjective expressing opinion comes before a factual or descriptive adjective.¹⁰**
- When two or more adjectives occur before a noun, an adjective expressing a general opinion comes after an adjective expressing a specific opinion.
- When writing from the standpoint of the present moment, it is essential to list recent events only.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth ed. (European Union, 2021), 50.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401D Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington D. C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- European Commission. *English Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth ed. European Union, 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.